

TEACHERS' AND STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVES ON THE ONLINE EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC CONTEXT – THE CASE OF AN EXTENSION OF A TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

Authors*: Adriana-Mirela SAVA ¹, Florina Petruța RUNCAN ², Monica BOGDAN ³
Position: Assoc. Prof., PhD¹, Eng. MSc Student², Lecturer, PhD³
University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Address: Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului Str., No. 28, Romania
Email: adriana.sava@mis.utcluj.ro ¹, runcan15@gmail.com ², monica.turcu@mis.utcluj.ro ³
Webpage: <http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – The paper offers a dual perspective, of both teachers and students, on various aspects related to the online educational activities organized and implemented in Bistrița university extension of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology/approach – Two surveys were carried out, targeting students and academic teachers of Bistrița extension of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca. 195 students and 80 teachers took part at the research, representing 49% of the university extension's entire student population and 64% of academics teaching at this extension in the 2020-2021 academic year.

Findings – Approximately one quarter of the teachers and only 7.7 percent of the students consider that online teaching has a higher effectiveness than traditional teaching. One third of teachers and only 17 percent of students are dissatisfied or very dissatisfied with their overall experience related to online educational activities, but 75 percent of teachers and almost 60 percent of students are satisfied or even very satisfied with their own performance during the online educational activities. The two populations have quite different perceptions regarding students' active participation during online classes.

Research limitations/implications – The results reflect the perspectives of teachers and students from only one of the four university extensions of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, the one located in the city of Bistrița.

Practical implications – The usefulness of these results is placed in the post-pandemic context, as the higher education system in Romania is in the process of being reconfigured to a certain extent, such that it adds an online dimension for complementing the traditional teaching and learning activities. The results can be used at Technical University of Cluj-Napoca's internal level, for supporting decisions related to organizing educational activities in its four extensions.

Originality/value – This article contributes to enriching the literature on educational processes at higher education level in the COVID-19 pandemic context, providing evidence from one university extension of one of the largest technical universities in Romania and encompassing the perspectives of two essential stakeholders of these processes, students and teachers.

Key words: pandemic, higher education, online education.

Introduction

Two years and a half after the COVID-19 pandemic emerged, it is clearer than ever that this sanitary crisis raised unprecedented challenges to both individuals and organizations across the globe. Most of the individuals worldwide were suddenly confronted with challenges on various levels, from health to social and emotional issues, from work-related aspects to financial ones, and as such, they had to reconfigure the activities related to almost every aspect of their lives, both at personal and professional levels.

In particular, education institutions and students at all educational levels, from primary education to higher education one, were almost overnight confronted with a new reality they have never experienced before and were forced to identify solutions for carrying out educational activities in completely

unparalleled uncertainty conditions. The transition from face-to-face educational activities to online ones was extremely abrupt and challenging for all the stakeholders involved in the educational processes.

The body of research and literature that emerged in these new conditions, addressing the impact of challenges faced by the educational system on its stakeholders is very rich, bringing evidence of the effect of the pandemic crisis on the educational, social or emotional lives of these stakeholders, especially on students and teachers. Romania's particular situation is not an exception in this context, with various researches carried out in order to investigate the perceptions of students or teachers about the online teaching and learning processes generated by the pandemic crisis (Coman et al., 2020; Edelhauser and Lupu-Dima, 2021; Potra et al., 2021; Alexa et al., 2022; Curelaru, Curelaru and Cristea, 2022; Deaconu and Olah, 2022; Gavriliuță, Dalban and Ioan, 2022; Spunei, Frumușanu, Muntean and Mărginean, 2022).

The Technical University of Cluj-Napoca (TUCN) is one of the largest technical universities in Romania, with more than 18000 students enrolled in undergraduate and master programs in the 2021-2022 academic year and over 900 academic and research staff. The university has 12 faculties in two university centers in Cluj-Napoca and Baia Mare, as well as four university extensions in four major cities in the region: Alba Iulia, Bistrița, Satu Mare and Zalău (Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, 2022). The study programs which TUCN organizes in its four university extensions follow the same authorization and accreditation process as all the other programs that are part of TUCN's educational offer in Cluj-Napoca.

Bistrița extension is the largest of the TUCN's four university extensions according to number of students. Its educational offer includes four undergraduate programs and two professional master programs coordinated by two of the TUCN faculties - Faculty of Industrial Engineering, Robotics and Production Management (three undergraduate programs and two master programs) and Faculty of Electrical Engineering (one undergraduate program). The four programs offered in Bistrița extension at undergraduate level are "Industrial Economic Engineering", "Robotics", "Digital Production Systems" and "Medical Engineering", whereas the two master programs are "Robotics" and "Management Quality and Engineering".

The students enrolled at TUCN's extensions, Bistrița extension included, follow the same curricula, obtain the same engineering bachelor or master degrees like their colleagues enrolled at the university's faculties in Cluj-Napoca and in addition, most of the academic teachers that teach in these extensions are the same teachers that carry out educational activities in Cluj-Napoca. However, the extensions also present some specific features, one of the most important being that the schedule of educational activities is not the same as the one adopted for activities with students in Cluj-Napoca. The TUCN's undergraduate students in Cluj-Napoca attend educational activities from Monday to Friday, their school schedule typically starts in the morning and usually meet an academic teacher once or twice a week, during the entire semester, for an average of two hours each week for every lecture or practical activity within the context of a specific subject.

On the other hand, at TUCN's extensions the educational activities usually start at noon and can continue up to nine o'clock in the evening and classes can also take place on Saturdays, not only on weekdays. This schedule fits the specific needs of the extensions' students, as many of these students, especially those in the 3rd or 4th year of their undergraduate studies, not to mention the ones enrolled in master programs, already have jobs and they need to combine their activities and responsibilities as employees with the demands of being higher education students. In addition, most of the academic teachers teaching at Bistrița extension make the commute from Cluj-Napoca to Bistrița, which is located 120 kilometers away from Cluj-Napoca and therefore they don't commute to the extension to carry out only a class of two hours with the students and come back to Cluj-Napoca, but rather the activities of their subject are organized in a modular schedule, with one teacher having activities for maybe six to eight hours per day, with the same students, for one, two or even three consecutive days, which means that the teacher usually remains overnight in Bistrița.

Before the pandemic, the educational activities in TUCN took place in a face-to-face traditional manner, with all the activities being held at university. In March 2020 the Romanian government adopted various measures for reducing the spread of the new coronavirus, based on social distancing, which also included closing the educational units. As a result, TUCN also entered an emergency online educational mode.

In TUCN, like in all other higher education institutions from Romania, the transition from face-to-face courses to online education initially represented an urgent measure adopted to ensure the continuity of educational activities, with both students and professors not knowing what expectations to have from this transition, nor for how long this solution was going to be used. The transition obviously raised significant challenges for both students and teachers.

On the 11th of March 2022, when TUCN suspended all face-to-face educational activities, the second semester of the 2019-2020 academic year had begun for only a couple of weeks. Given the pandemic situation in Romania, the country entered an emergency state until later in May that year and hence the remaining of the second semester, including the summer session of exams, took place exclusively online. By the fall of 2020, the decision of how to conduct the educational activities in the 2020-2021 academic year was left up to each university in Romania. TUCN decided to begin the academic year in a hybrid mode, with online lectures and face-to-face practical activities (laboratories, seminars and projects). However, only three weeks into the new academic year, the pandemic situation forced the university to switch again to a full online education mode and this remained in place for the entire 2020-2021 academic year.

Research methodology

A research was conducted with the aim of exploring students' and teaching staff's perceptions regarding the educational activities that took place online at Bistrița extension in the COVID-19 pandemic context. Because we wanted to capture the perceptions of both educational stakeholders, two different populations were chosen for investigation: students enrolled in both undergraduate or master studies at Bistrița branch, as well as teachers teaching at this university extension. The two targeted populations consisted of 398 students enrolled in one of the specializations offered at Bistrița extension in the 2020-2021 academic year and of 125 teaching staff that carried out educational activities at this extension in the same academic year.

Among the main research objectives were identification of the perceptions of both stakeholders, students and academic teachers, about various elements related to the educational activities implemented at Bistrița extension: the perceived main advantages and disadvantages of online education, effectiveness of online education compared to traditional one, their perception regarding students' active participation during online classes, their satisfaction level related to everything they have experienced in relation to online education, as well as their satisfaction level with their own performance during online teaching activities.

Two very similar questionnaires were used as research instruments, one targeting students and the second one addressing teachers. There were small differences between these questionnaires, according to the different populations they were developed for. Data collection took place online, using Google Forms platform for collecting responses, at the end of June 2021. At the moment of data collection phase, both the investigated students and teachers populations had experienced online educational activities for more than one year, in the second semester of the 2019-2020 academic year, when Romania was in state of emergency due to the pandemic, as well as during the 2020-2021 university year, when Romania was no longer in emergency state, but in state of alert. The exception from this situation is represented by 1st year undergraduate students, who began their academic studies only in the fall of 2020. Following the data collection phase, 195 responses were obtained from students and 80 responses from the teaching staff population, which account for response rates of 49% of the entire student population and 64% of the teachers' population.

This paper next presents some of the most significant results of the research and attempts to compare the results obtained at both populations' levels.

Results

The main socio-demographic characteristics of both investigated samples are presented in table 1. The distribution of students' sample by gender shows that 54.9 percent of the respondent students are males, whereas the remaining 45.1 percent are females. Almost 70 percent of students have between 18 and 24 years, another 22.1 percent of the sample have ages between 25 and 34 years and the 8.7 remaining percent includes more mature students, that are between 35 and 45 years old. The majority of students, representing 61.5 percent, have residence in urban areas and the remaining 38.5 percent of students live in rural areas. The large majority of students, 82.6 percent, is represented by students

of the Faculty of Industrial Engineering, Robotics and Management Production, with the remaining 17.4 percent being students of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering; this structure of students' sample by their faculty is explained by the difference in the number of undergraduate and master programs offered by each of the two faculties at Bistrița extension. The repartition of undergraduate students by their year of study is relatively balanced. Finally, the distribution of the sample according to students' program of study is the following one: Industrial Economic Engineering (undergraduate, 34.4 percent), Digital Production Systems (undergraduate, 21 percent), Medical Engineering (undergraduate, 16.9 percent), Robotics (undergraduate 14.9 percent), Robotics (master, 6.7 percent), Quality Management and Engineering (master, 6.2 percent).

Table 1. Characteristics of the two samples of students and teachers

Students (195 respondents)						
Gender	Male 54.9%			Female 45.1%		
Age	18-24 years 69.2%		25-34 years 22.1%		35-45 years 8.7%	
Residence environment	Urban 61.5%			Rural 38.5%		
Year of study	Undergraduate 1 st year 19%	Undergraduate 2 nd year 22.1%	Undergraduate 3 rd year 26.2%	Undergraduate 4 th year 20.5%	Master 1 st year 9.7%	Master 2 nd year 2.6%
Academic teachers (80 respondents)						
Gender	Male 65%			Female 35%		
Age	25-34 years 8.8%	35-44 years 51.3%	45-55 years 22.5%	55-64 years 12.5%	65 years or more 5%	
Type of staff	Tenured teaching staff 83.8%			Associated teaching staff 16.2%		
Teaching degree	Assistant professor 7.5%	Lecturer 47.5%	Associate professor 21.3%	Professor 16.3%	Not applicable 7.5%	
Years of study which they teach	Undergraduate 1 st year 28.7%	Undergraduate 2 nd year 41.3%	Undergraduate 3 rd year 41.3%	Undergraduate 4 th year 36.3%	Master 1 st year 15%	Master 2 nd year 11.3%

The other investigated sample, of 80 academic teachers, includes 65 percent males and 35 percent females. Approximately half of the sample is formed by teachers between 35 and 44 years old, with other 22.5 percent having between 45 and 54 years. A large majority of 83.8 percent consists of tenured teaching staff, the remaining 16.2 percent being associated teaching staff. In what concerns the academic titles of the respondents, 47.5 percent are lecturers, 21.3 percent associate professors and 16.3 percent are full professors. In addition, the structure of the sample of teachers by the faculties where they are affiliated shows that the majority of the respondents are teachers of the Faculty of Industrial Engineering, Robotics and Production Management (68.8 percent), while the remaining teachers are affiliated to other faculties, like Electrical Engineering (13.8 percent), Materials and Environmental Engineering (7.5 percent), Automotive, Mechatronics and Mechanical Engineering (6.3 percent) and Automation and Computer Science (3.8 percent).

When asked to express their opinions on the effectiveness of online teaching in comparison to traditional educational activities (figure 1), it seems that online teaching is considered more ineffective than face-to-face teaching, according to the opinions expressed by 53.8 percent of teachers and 44.6 of students. A share of 14.4 percent of students sample considers that online teaching is much more ineffective, however no single teacher selected this option. A third of the students and 22.5 percent of teachers consider that teaching in both environments, online and onsite, has the same effectiveness. Only around 6 percent of each sample believe that online teaching is more effective. An interesting discrepancy is noted for the "much more effective" option, with 17.5 percent of teachers considering that the

effectiveness of online teaching is much higher than that of traditional teaching, but this opinion is shared by only 1.5 percent of the students.

Figure 1. Perception on effectiveness of online teaching compared to traditional teaching

Regarding the active participation of students during the educational activities that took place online, it seems there is a perception gap between how students perceive their own participation during classes and how teachers actually assess their involvement during online activities (figure 2). Most of the students, representing 44.6 percent of the sample, considered themselves as being active during the online educational activities, whereas 41.3 percent of the teachers sample perceived the students as being not so active. Roughly one third of each sample perceived students' active participation at an average level, 36.3 percent of teachers and 31.3 percent of students. While other 8.7 percent of students rated their participation as very active, it can be noted that not a single teacher perceived students' participation during online classes as being very active.

Figure 2. Perception regarding students' active participation in online educational activities

In what concerns respondents' overall satisfaction with everything they have experienced in relation to the online educational activities (figure 3), the largest shares of each sample consist of those respondents that declared they were satisfied in this respect, 33.8 percent of teachers and 41 percent of students. Another third of each sample expressed an average satisfaction, being neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their overall online teaching and learning experience. However, a notable difference can be noted among those who had an unsatisfactory overall experience with online educational activities, with 30 percent of the teachers being dissatisfied in comparison to only 14.4 percent of students. In addition, small shares of the two samples used the anchors of the used scale, very dissatisfied or very satisfied, to rate their satisfaction level. Within these results, the very low percentage of teachers that were very satisfied with their overall online educational experience should be noted (only 1.3 percent).

Figure 3. Overall satisfaction with the entire experience related to online educational activities

Figure 4 presents the overall satisfaction of the two groups of respondents regarding their own performance during online educational activities. The majority of each sample of respondents, 58.8 percent of teachers and 50.8 percent of students, are satisfied with their performance. The highest level of satisfaction, very satisfied, is perceived by 16.3 percent of teachers and 8.7 percent of students. An average satisfaction level was indicated by slightly more students (24.1 percent) than teachers (17.5 percent). It should also be noted that only small shares of the two samples were dissatisfied or very dissatisfied with their own performance and additionally no single teacher was very dissatisfied with his own performance during the educational activities that took place in the online environment.

As the research was carried out in June 2021, close to the end of the 2020-2021 academic year, the respondents were also asked which option of carrying out educational activities they feel would be more appropriate for them in the next academic year (figure 5). Hybrid education was the most preferred option for 58.8 percent of teachers and almost half of students (47.7 percent). A little over one third of the teachers (36.3 percent) would have preferred for the activities in the next academic year to take place exclusively online, with 27.7 percent of students considering this option as the most suitable one for them. A much higher discrepancy between the two samples can be noted in relation to those that expressed their preference for exclusively online educational activities, almost one quarter of students (24.6 percent), but only 5 percent of teachers. However, the pandemic reality in the next academic year, 2021-2022, enabled TUCN to begin the new academic year in a hybrid regime, both in Cluj-Napoca and at university's extensions, with online lectures and face-to-face practical activities (laboratories, seminars and projects). This hybrid system was in place in TUCN until March 2022, when after almost two years in state of alert due to the pandemic, Romania ended the state of alert and started lifting pandemic restrictions. Since then, TUCN switched back to a completely onsite system, with all educational activities taking place face-to-face.

Figure 4. Satisfaction with own performance during online educational activities

Figure 5. Preference for educational activities in the 2021-2022 academic year

Both teachers and students were also asked about the advantages and disadvantages of online educational activities. For teachers, the most important benefit of online teaching consists in the flexibility it gives for participants to connect from everywhere, according to 88.8 percent of teachers. Other important advantages, from teachers' point of view, consist in eliminating the need for teachers to commute between Cluj-Napoca and Bistrița, an advantage mentioned by almost half of teachers and which is completely expected, as most of the teachers that teach at Bistrița extension have to commute between the two cities, which are 120 kilometers apart. The ease of use of online applications and the large range of applications also represent advantages of online teaching for teachers. Flexibility is the most significant advantage of online teaching for 93.3 percent of students as well. Another important advantage in students' opinion was the possibility of having online exams, an opinion that was shared

by almost 70 percent of students and includes even the fact that almost 15 percent of students considered online exams had a reduced difficulty compared to the classic face-to-face ones. The large range of applications that can be used for online teaching and learning, as well as the easiness of using these applications, are advantages identified by 41 percent and 37.4 percent respectively of students as well.

On the other hand, teachers' perspective on the disadvantages of online educational activities pointed out that the two most important shortcomings of this education system are reduced interaction with students, an opinion shared by 77.5 percent of teachers and students' low motivation level (68.7 percent of teachers). Lower shares of the teachers' sample indicated other disadvantages, such as reduced interaction with work colleagues (36.3 percent), weak Internet connection (30 percent) and the fact that some of the students did not turn on their camera during online teaching activities. In their turn, for students the most important shortcoming of online teaching was the reduced interaction with their colleagues (according to 60.5 percent of students), followed by a weak Internet connection (50.8 percent), low focus capacity (46.2 percent) and reduced interaction with their teachers (45.1 percent). Students also perceived a lack of motivation for educational activities (one third of the students) and felt they had a higher volume of homework to do in the online environment (29.2 percent).

Discussion and conclusions

Education at all levels has been one of the most affected areas after the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic. Teachers and students worldwide were suddenly confronted with unprecedented challenges for continuing their educational activities.

This paper presented the results of a research carried out at Bistrița extension of the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania, providing a dual perspective, of both teachers and students, on the educational activities that had to be organized and implemented in the online environment, as a consequence of the pandemic. The obtained results expressed the opinions of almost half of students of the university extension and of 64% of all the teachers that carried out educational activities at Bistrița extension in the 2020-2021 academic year.

The results showed that teachers were less satisfied than students with their overall experience related to online educational activities in the pandemic context, but had a slightly higher degree of satisfaction with their own performance during online educational activities than students. A gap was noted in the perception of both populations about students' active participation during online classes; half of the teachers perceived that students were not at all active or just a little active during these activities, whereas roughly half of students considered themselves as being active or very active during activities.

The results also showed that a quarter of teachers and only 7.7 percent of students considered that online teaching is more effective than traditional teaching, with only 5 percent of teachers and a quarter of students expressing their preferences for fully online teaching activities in the next academic year. These results suggest that online educational activities represent a suitable method for teaching and learning in technical higher education, but more as a complementary approach to traditional face-to-face education.

Flexibility is seen as the main advantage of online education by both teachers and students, as this system gives them the option to join the educational activities from wherever they are. The second most important advantage for teachers was the fact that online activities made the commute between Cluj-Napoca and Bistrița no longer necessary, the distance between two cities being of 120 kilometers, with no highway connecting the cities. From students' side, the second most important benefit brought by online education resided in the possibility of having online exams, which some of them perceived as being easier than traditional face-to-face evaluations.

In what concerns the main shortcomings of online education, the two most important disadvantages for the investigated teachers were the reduced interaction they were able to have with students and a lower motivation level of students, which made it even harder for teachers to draw and keep students' attention in the online environment. On the other hand, students considered that lack of interaction with their colleagues represented the main disadvantage of online teaching, but they also identified other important disadvantages like a weak Internet connection, which could be explained by the fact that 40 percent of the investigated students lived in rural areas, the existence of various distractions that did not

help them to keep their concentration and attention during online activities and reduced interaction with their teachers.

A similar research was carried out by the authors, the targeted populations being the teachers and students from a faculty of the same university, but located in Cluj-Napoca. The results of this research will be disseminated in other papers and a future path for research could rely in investigating if there are significant differences in the perspectives of teachers and students from the faculty in Cluj-Napoca and those from Bistrița university extension.

The study results can provide TUCN with valuable insight for the post-pandemic reality as well, which could be used at university level to design online and hybrid educational activities better adapted to both teachers' and students' perspectives on teaching and learning in the online environment. This aspect is important as in Romania there currently are legislative initiatives for a possible hybridization of higher education.

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